

Development of the CAMELOT approach for considering methodological limitations of qualitative research in the context of GRADE-CERQual and qualitative evidence syntheses – protocol

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Background

Qualitative evidence syntheses (QES)- sometimes called systematic reviews of qualitative evidence- is a term for the broad group of methods for systematically synthesising the findings from multiple primary qualitative studies. QES are used increasingly alongside reviews of effectiveness, and more recently as stand-alone products (1). QES has recently become an important method for incorporating qualitative research into decision-making processes, including global guideline development and policy formulation (2). The 'Confidence in the Evidence from Reviews of Qualitative research' (GRADE-CERQual) approach was developed to support the use of findings from QES in decision-making. The approach aims to transparently and systematically assess how much confidence to place in findings from qualitative evidence syntheses. It was initially developed and piloted in 2013, and since then has been cited by more than 700 papers and reviews. The current version of the GRADE-CERQual approach bases its assessment of confidence on four components (3):

- (1) the methodological limitations of the individual studies contributing to a review finding;
- (2) the adequacy of data supporting a review finding (the degree of richness and / or scope of the evidence and quantity of data supporting a review finding);
- (3) the coherence of each review finding (the extent to which a review finding is based on data that is similar within and across multiple individual studies and / or incorporates convincing explanations for any variations across individual studies); and
- (4) the relevance of a review finding (the extent to which the evidence supporting a review finding is applicable to the context specified in the review question).

These four components have equal importance when assessing how much confidence to place in findings from qualitative evidence syntheses. In this study, we focus on the first component: assessing the methodological limitations of the primary studies feeding into each synthesised finding. More specifically, we are interested in studying the evidence base that increases our own confidence in the power of identified appraisal criteria to improve the quality of qualitative research.

An assessment of the methodological limitations of included studies is key to the overall assessment of evidence from qualitative evidence syntheses. However, despite the existence of a variety of checklists and tools (e.g., (4, 5)), there is no overall consensus on the best approach to assessing the methodological limitations of qualitative studies. The Cochrane Qualitative & Implementation Methods Group's (QIMG) supplemental guidance suggests a set of criteria that can be used when selecting an existing tool, although none are a complete fit for the intended purpose of supporting the assessment of the GRADE-CERQual methodological limitations component (6). Guided by this, authors of Cochrane qualitative evidence syntheses have adapted an appraisal tool (7), used a familiar tool (8) or picked a tool from a list (9). This lack of a uniform approach is similar to the

situation for systematic reviews of effectiveness over twenty years ago, where over 30 checklists were being used to assess the “quality” of randomised trials (10). To address this lack of consistency and to reach consensus, a working group of methodologists, editors and review authors developed the risk of bias tool that is now used for Cochrane Reviews of effectiveness (11) and is a key component of the GRADE tool (12). While the Cochrane risk of bias tool is still based on review authors’ judgements, it encourages review authors to be transparent and systematic in how they appraise the methodological limitations of primary studies. Similar efforts are needed to develop an appraisal tool appropriate to assess the methodological limitations of primary qualitative studies.

Developers of the Cochrane risk of bias tool followed an evidence-based approach to tool development by explicitly incorporating empirical evidence regarding the importance of specific components of study design and conduct, and the impact of these on risk of bias in study-level estimates of effects [13]. It is critical that further development of an approach to consider risks to rigour in qualitative research also aims to locate evidence to help us identify the most important components. In general, the criteria included in critical appraisal tools for qualitative studies are inadequate for GRADE-CERQual as they are neither based on evidence nor do they encapsulate explicit hypotheses regarding the relationships between components of qualitative study design and conduct and the trustworthiness of the study findings. The CAMELOT project seeks to address this gap by building on work thus far and undertaking the research needed to produce an evidence-informed approach to consider risk to rigour in qualitative research.

Project aim

The aim of the CAMELOT project is to identify or develop an evidence-informed approach to critically appraise primary qualitative research within the context of qualitative evidence synthesis and to support the assessment of the GRADE-CERQual methodological limitations domain.

Research questions

1. What are the existing critical appraisal checklists and tools for primary qualitative research?
2. Which criteria are included in existing critical appraisal tools?
3. What is the evidence that criteria included in existing critical appraisal tools are good indicators of trustworthiness or rigor of qualitative research?
4. What is the consensus of relevant stakeholders on key criteria for critically appraising primary qualitative research within the context of qualitative evidence synthesis and GRADE-CERQual?

Methodology

The CAMELOT project will use a four-stage model to develop an evidence-informed approach for critically appraising primary qualitative research in the context of qualitative evidence synthesis and GRADE-CERQual: define the issue, identify and review existing tools, conduct a consensus-meeting process and, refine the tool via piloting (13). This very much reflects a human-centred approach to product development whereby the needs and experiences of the users or stakeholders drive the development (14).

The methods reported in this protocol focus on stages 2-4 of the process. Stage 1 is briefly described below, however, it was completed in 2019. The protocol and completed review are published and available (15).

Stage 1. Identifying and mapping existing critical appraisal tools and checklists

We systematically searched for critical appraisal tools and checklists for primary qualitative research published between 2006 and 2018. We began by including tools identified by an earlier systematic review (16). We conducted framework synthesis using the criteria included in the critical appraisal tools as data. The starting point for the framework synthesis was the Critical Appraisal Skills Programme checklist for qualitative research, as this is a commonly used tool among QES teams (17). We identified 102 critical appraisal tools and 22 criteria across the tools (15). The results of the review are available here.

Stage 2. Identifying evidence for included tool elements

In stage 2 we will address research question 3: *What is the evidence that criteria included in existing critical appraisal tools are good indicators of trustworthiness or rigor of qualitative research?* We will establish a working group of researchers representing diverse and relevant backgrounds (e.g., fields of research, qualitative traditions, methodological expertise). We will hold a series of meetings to:

1. Discuss which of the components identified from the review (Stage 1) are relevant for a critical appraisal tool within the context of qualitative evidence synthesis and to support the GRADE-CERQual methodological limitations component.
2. Discuss evidence for relevant components to support their inclusion in a critical appraisal tool (i.e., do concerns regarding component A influence our confidence in a review finding?)

Methods

Each working group member will choose 3-4 criteria from the list of criteria for appraising qualitative research. For each criterion, the responsible group member will search for evidence supporting/refuting the criterions' relevance to the trustworthiness of qualitative research. AB will develop a minimum search protocol for use with each criterion.

Search Strategy

Will differ for each criterion. There will be no date limit on the searches.

Publications will be included if they:

- Discuss the inclusion of specific components of critical appraisal tools
- Discuss empirical evidence for importance of components identified in stage 1 and/or how components in stage 1 influence qualitative research. The types of evidence for this search will be indicated as belonging to one of the following categories:
 - Empirical: studies examining how a criterion influences the trustworthiness of qualitative research
 - Practical: systematic reviews or primary studies that can support/refute how a criterion influenced the findings of the study
 - Theoretical: publications discussing how a criterion should/could (not) influence the trustworthiness of qualitative research
 - Proxy: publications from quantitative research that discuss similar/comparable domains and their influence on findings from quantitative research

Additionally, studies that discuss or explore how different elements or criteria for assessing the methodological limitations of qualitative studies impact on the trustworthiness of study findings (e.g., [16-19]) will also be included.

Data extraction:

We will extract data from each relevant publication on the following:

- Title
- Author details
- Year
- Component being discussed
- Any information regarding the influence of the component on the trustworthiness of qualitative research
- Any information regarding reasons for the inclusion of the component in a critical appraisal tool

Data analysis:

For each identified criterion, we will summarize the empirical/theoretical/practical/proxy evidence for its inclusion in checklists/tools/guides for methodological quality of qualitative research. The lead team member will fill out a template (see draft version below) to be presented to the group for discussion (2-3 days before meeting). The lead team member will present the criterion and the

results of their search to the group during a 1-2 hour working meeting. The group will discuss the results of the search and decide (a) whether to include the criterion and (b) how to present the criterion. Given that the discussion of one criterion may result in the creation of an additional criterion, the list and responsibilities for investigation will be updated after each meeting. We will discuss and resolve 1-2 criteria at each working meeting.

We will then attempt to link these criteria to any empirical evidence on their impacts on the trustworthiness of findings from individual qualitative studies (tools may assess factors that have no explicit link with methodological limitations, such as informed consent, and these will not be considered here). We anticipate that little or no empirical evidence is available for some potentially important elements. For these elements, we will use qualitative research principles (e.g. the use of purposive data sampling to select information rich cases [20]) to develop hypotheses on how they may impact on the trustworthiness of study findings.

We will publish findings from each meeting on a wiki page to ensure transparency and encourage collaboration with other researchers who are interested in and/or working on similar questions.

Deliverables:

We will consolidate a list of the criteria consistently identified as important for critically appraising qualitative research.

Stage 3: Consensus process to agree on CAMELOT criteria

It is generally considered good practice to involve experts and other stakeholders when developing methodological guidance and tools (13). We will therefore undertake an online Delphi survey (eDelphi) in order to achieve consensus on the consolidated list of proposed CAMELOT criteria (result of Stage 2 work). This stage is intended to address research question 4: *What is the consensus of relevant stakeholders on key criteria for critically appraising primary qualitative research within the context of qualitative evidence synthesis and GRADE-CERQual?*. The Delphi technique is commonly used to gather opinions and feedback from a group of relevant experts, and to achieve consensus on a product (18). We will follow guidance set forth by Conducting and Reporting Delphi Studies (19). This Delphi process will have three parts.

1. **Introductory seminar:** In this stage we will introduce the project to panel members.
2. **eDelphi survey:** In this stage we will conduct three rounds of the eDelphi process to exclude irrelevant criteria, and compile and prioritize relevant criteria.
3. **Consensus meeting:** In this stage we will hold an online workshop to confirm the list of relevant criteria to be included in CAMELOT, the terminology to be used for each criterion, and discuss possible methods and guidance for assessing each criterion.

We will use the eDelphi method to reach consensus on which criteria should be used to consider the trustworthiness of qualitative research included in qualitative evidence syntheses. Questionnaires are presented to panel members in a series of rounds. The first questionnaire will be based on the findings from stage 2 (described above). Each subsequent questionnaire will be based on feedback from the panel's responses to the previous questionnaire. The major advantage of this consensus-reaching method is that respondents remain anonymous, thereby encouraging honest answers unlikely to be biased from peer pressure or majority opinions (20). The result of the Delphi will be a list of criteria to include in CAMELOT.

Stages 3.1, 3.2 and 3.3 Sampling and recruitment

We will aim to include a diverse set of panellists in order to represent diverse academic disciplines (e.g., education, health, social work), experience, roles (academics, decision makers, other stakeholders), familiarity with GRADE/-CERQual, systematic reviews and qualitative research. We will recruit 56 methodological experts and 49 other stakeholders with experience producing or using evidence from systematic reviews and/or qualitative evidence syntheses.

Methodological experts

We will send invitations to 75 methodological experts with experience related to qualitative research, evidence synthesis, and/or critical appraisal and methodological development work. We will use purposive sampling via the research team's professional networks. We will also ask experts to suggest other experts (snowballing technique). We will aim for a recruitment rate of 75% (N=56). We expect attrition during stages 3.1 and 3.2 to be 40%. We will then have a final sample of at least 33 participants.

We will send invitations to potential panellists informing them of the scope and objectives of the project. Those who agree to participate will fill out confidentiality, consent and conflict of interest forms, and write a short reflexivity statement (see Appendix 1 adapted from Viswanathan 2014(21) and Glenton 2022 (22)). Panelists will be offered the opportunity to be acknowledged or a role as co-author on any eventual papers when contributions warrant so.

Other stakeholders

We will send invitations to 70 stakeholders including researchers with experience related to evidence synthesis and users of evidence syntheses. These two groups will be separated due to the methodological nature of the criteria being explored. We will identify these stakeholders via professional networks, author lists on systematic reviews from Cochrane and Campbell

Collaboration, and other relevant research institutions. We will aim for a recruitment rate of 70% (N=49) and expect attrition of approximately 33%, with a final sample of at least 32 stakeholders. In total we aim to have a final sample of 65 stakeholders involved in the complete process.

Stage 3.1. Introductory Seminar

We will invite panel members to a digital introductory seminar. During this seminar we will present panel members with a short description of the activities and research up until this point. We will outline the criteria that will be sent out in the eDelphi (Stage 3.2). We will also present an overview of the eDelphi process and consensus meeting. This seminar will be recorded and shared with panel members who were unable to attend.

Stage 3.2. Online Delphi (eDelphi)

We will conduct three rounds of the eDelphi survey. We will use the first round to achieve consensus on a list of proposed criteria (with the opportunity to identify missing criteria). The second round will focus on achieving consensus on describing and/or prioritizing any eventual relationship between criteria (promoted from the first round), and the third round will focus on selecting and prioritizing important points to include under guidance for each criteria. We will use the survey platform provided by Calibrium (calibrium.com; (23)). We have chosen this platform based on the findings and experience from previous studies which have compared and used different eDelphi software (24).

Procedure

Following recruitment of panel members (see sampling and sample above), we will conduct the Delphi study online using the platform described above provided by Calibrium (23).

Each panel member (respondent) will be sent a link to the Delphi study in an email with details related to due date and expectations. After logging in, the panel member will be presented with a questionnaire. In the first round the questionnaire will contain items related to the findings from Stage 2. In the second and third rounds respondents will be presented with similar items, in addition to any items that arose from the previous round. They will also be able to see the most popular responses from previous rounds together with their own response and a visual representation of frequency of responses in the previous round.

Data collection

Each round will take approximately 4 weeks (total 12 weeks). Three rounds is considered ideal in order to avoid respondent fatigue while still ensuring maximum opportunity to achieve consensus

among respondents (20, 25). We will send respondents reminders via email two weeks after each round has begun and three days before the due date to those who have not yet completed.

For each round, the respondent will be presented with potential items to be included in a critical appraisal tool and asked to rate which items they consider to be important (using a 4 point Likert scale for each item)(20). Specifically, respondents will be asked to focus on the following for each round:

Round 1: Identify which items are related to reporting vs methodological limitations

Round 2: Identifying which items are important for considering methodological limitations and trustworthiness of qualitative research

Round 3: Prioritizing which items (based on rounds 1 and 2) should be included in a tool to consider methodological limitations of primary qualitative research within the context of qualitative evidence synthesis and to support the GRADE-CERQual methodological limitations component.

In round 1, respondents will also have the opportunity to add additional criteria not present in the current list. We will only collect quantitative data from the Likert scale assessments, as well as collecting responses to the open ended question “are there any criteria missing from this list” in round 1.

Data analysis

Data will be collated automatically after each round and fed back to panel members at the subsequent round. After the final round, we will prepare descriptive statistics for the data (frequency and percentage of responses) illustrating level of consensus for each criterion. This will be sent to panel members before the consensus meeting. Criteria with a consensus level greater than 60% will be promoted for consideration during the final consensus meeting.

Stage 3.3. Consensus meeting

Following the final round of the eDelphi process, panellists will be asked to comment on the final draft in plenum delivered digitally via webinar. We will invite between 10 and 20 panellists to participate (based on degree of participation in previous rounds). The session will be recorded and a summary of the discussions will be made available as an appendix to the published results of the Delphi process.

The goals of this meeting will be to

- Establish a list of components to be used in the CAMELOT approach
- Discuss way forward for producing and disseminating CAMELOT approach and guidance

Meeting procedure

- Present results of Delphi process (list of CAMELOT components)
- Discuss rationale for including each component
- Vote on any controversial components

Stage 4. Piloting and user testing

Based on the results of the eDelphi and consensus meeting we will publish a beta version of the CAMELOT approach. We will use human-centred design methods to refine the approach (14). This will comprise presenting at workshops and webinars, where we will also recruit review teams to use CAMELOT. We will use the think-aloud method and conduct semi-structured interviews focused on useability and understandability to gather feedback from review teams and refine the tool based on feedback (26, 27). We will use an adapted version of Morville's honeycomb model to analyse feedback from user tests (28-30). This will be an iterative process. The final version of CAMELOT will be made available in a scientific publication.

Ethical issues

We will apply for ethical approval if deemed appropriate or necessary by the Norwegian Regional Ethical Committee.

All panel members will receive a study information sheet and will be asked to sign a consent form. Panel members will agree during the introductory seminar how intellectual contribution will be recognized in any eventual publications or other project outputs.

Reflexivity

The researchers involved in this project represent diverse academic disciplines which allows for varied perspectives on all stages of the development of CAMELOT (e.g., nursing, information science, social welfare, public health, medical sociology). Most of the researchers are also co-founders and co-ordinators of the GRADE-CERQual approach. Their positionality offers an advantageous perspective in relation to what review teams are looking for when conducting critical appraisal of primary studies within the context of qualitative evidence syntheses. Three of the researchers sit in the Cochrane Qualitative and Implementation Methods Group (JN, AB, RG). Four of the authors (JN, AB, IS, KH) have experience with Delphi processes. The research team occupy various roles in relation to national and international evidence synthesis activities.

Proposed dissemination strategies:

- Involvement of relevant Cochrane and Campbell groups and other stakeholders throughout the development process
- Presentations at Cochrane and Campbell Colloquia and other relevant meetings
- Publication of papers in open-access journals
- Close collaboration with the Cochrane Qualitative and Implementation Methods Group, thereby supporting incorporation of methodological developments into updates of the Cochrane Handbook and supplementary guidance

Anticipated implications of the proposal for Cochrane Review Groups and their authors

An increasing number of Cochrane Review Groups are including qualitative research in or alongside Cochrane effectiveness reviews. The outputs of this project will provide the foundation for a “qualitative risk of bias tool”, analogous to that used for effectiveness studies. This tool will have a potentially high impact through improving the quality, interpretation and use of Cochrane qualitative evidence syntheses.

Furthermore, the development of a “qualitative risk of bias tool” is critical to the ongoing development of GRADE-CERQual, with the goal of becoming a standardised approach for use by Cochrane authors. The future impacts of GRADE-CERQual on the conduct and quality of Cochrane qualitative evidence syntheses may achieve similar magnitude to that of GRADE for Cochrane systematic reviews of effectiveness.

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Appendix 1. Conflicts of interest form (adapted from Viswanathan 2014 and Glenton 2022)

Please answer the following questions to the best of your existing knowledge. The questions are not intended to require additional research or time-intensive inquiry beyond your current awareness.

Personal beliefs

1. Do you have strongly held beliefs related to the topic area that would make it difficult for you to consider alternative conclusions on this comparative effectiveness review in an unbiased manner?

Yes No

If yes, please explain.

Previously published opinions

2. Have you ever authored, coauthored, or publicly provided an opinion related to this topic area?

Yes No

If yes, what were those views and where were they made?

Personal relationships

3. Do you have personal relationships that would make it difficult for you participate in this project in an unbiased manner?

Yes No

If yes, please explain.

Institutional relationships

4. To the best of your knowledge, could your institution benefit or be harmed based on the findings of this project?

Yes No Don't Know

If yes, please explain.

Career advancement

5. How would you characterize the support you would receive from your primary mentor, institution, or other entities, if your work generated a strong reaction from peers outside your institution?

Answer the following questions, if applicable:

Advocacy/policy positions

6. To the best of your knowledge, do you work for, or are you a member of an organization with a stated position (e.g., position statement, blog, editorial, legislature or legal testimony, or related document) related to this project?

Yes No

7. If yes to #6, are you involved in formulating/voting for positions?

Yes No

If yes to #6, could positive or negative findings of this project conflict with policies you have promoted or are obliged to follow?

Yes No Don't Know /Not Applicable

If yes to #6 or #7, please explain

Interspecialty variations in practice:

8. What is your primary job/specialty?

Reflexivity statement

Please describe any prior positions or projects and how they may influence the decisions you make at various points of this project. Please describe, where relevant, any strategies you will use to address these issues.